

A very simple explanation of the Missing Square Puzzle

(by Michel Fattersack)

The well-known Missing Square Puzzle is illustrated by the following picture :

(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Missing_square_puzzle)

When you rearrange the pieces of the figure, a white square appears in the B configuration...Where did it come from ? The explanation given everywhere on the web and also by generative AIs (Chatgpt, Claude, Gemini, etc) is based on the fact that, contrary to appearances, the hypotenuses of the red and blue triangles are not collinear. This explanation is not only laborious and incomprehensible to a child, but it is also incorrect.

Indeed, if we replace the two hypotenuses with arbitrary polygonal lines, the white square still appears in configuration B'. Therefore, the explanation based on the misalignment of the two hypotenuses does not explain the visual paradox at all.

For a person without a scientific background, or even a child, to truly understand where the paradox comes from, it is enough to point out that, once the blue and red triangles have been placed, the space to be filled in configuration A'' is a rectangle of $3 \times 5 = 15$ squares, while the space to be filled in configuration B'' is a rectangle of $2 \times 8 = 16$ squares. However, the combined area of the yellow and green pieces is 15 squares. Therefore, there is necessarily one missing square in configuration B''?

Quid Erat Demonstrandum